

USING NLP TO CREATE CORPUS-BASED VOCABULARY EXERCISES IN LATIN CLASSES

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Abstract

Learning a historical language is in itself different from learning a modern language in view of emphasizing the work on texts instead of everyday communication. Therefore, not only the expectations and motivation differ, but also the teaching methodology. Whereas learners of modern languages focus on language production, learners of Latin read or translate their texts. Because of the overall low frequency of occurrence of a Latin word or a phrase in this kind of learning environment, most students are often unfamiliar with a given word and therefore finally unable to translate the texts. To approach this underlying problem of Latin classes (in German high schools) we try to figure out

- whether corpus-based methods are more supportive in Latin vocabulary acquisition than other methods used in teaching languages and
- how corpus-based tasks might be (analogically and digitally) implemented in class.

Consequently, we adapt the methodology of data-driven (language) learning as an educational innovation for Latin classes. In this context, we reuse various tools from the Classics and the natural language processing community for the development of our corpus-based software (Machina Callida, <https://korpling.org/mc>). Simultaneously, we carried out different intervention studies using a design-based research approach. In these studies, we gained some interesting insights, e.g. that the majority of students fail to lemmatize words correctly. Likewise, we tested the user experience of our software receiving feedback from experts (teachers, students). Then, we used both kinds of results to improve the software constantly, e.g. readjusting the type of exercises or the order of tasks in our so-called vocabulary unit. Finally, we started a new study using the so-called vocabulary unit that presents both an example of how to implement – to some extent – data-driven learning into Latin classes and how to carry out an intervention study within the software. The results so far available indicate that students benefit a little more in their temporary learning outcome from using a context-based vocabulary task (cloze). Although the results are promising, we need to collect more data, esp. taking into account the individual learning progress (e.g. by implementing a user management).

Keywords: Data-driven learning, corpus-based exercises, Latin vocabulary acquisition, NLP, adaptive learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

In German high schools, almost 600 000 students learn Latin [1]. Following English and French, the historical language is still the third most important foreign language, esp. in grades 7 to 10. Consequently, there is a high demand for educational materials that support the language acquisition of Latin. Therefore, on the one hand publishing houses offer a vast number of different items like textbooks, exercise books or software, to assist the teaching and learning of Latin. On the other hand, teachers and students find enough (free) learning materials in the internet, e.g. explanatory videos or vocabulary tools. Despite all this support, teachers in schools and universities claim that students do not have enough vocabulary knowledge for understanding and translating Latin texts [2]. This raises the question why there is a gap between support and achievement in Latin vocabulary acquisition and how it might be overcome.

Analysing the circumstances of Latin as a subject in German schools, there are probably three major reasons for this long-lasting problem of vocabulary acquisition in Latin classes: a domain-specific reason, a scientific reason and a methodical reason. First of all, Latin as a historical language focuses on translation whereas reading and, more importantly, oral communication do not matter in German secondary schools [3, p. 13]. Thus, both teachers and students are not used to Latin language production (= lower level of language proficiency than in modern languages) and tend to think cross-lingually (Latin – German) rather than intra-lingually (Latin – Latin). Secondly, there is a lack of research and empirical studies on learning Latin, esp. in the German-speaking community [4, p. 1]. In addition, linguistics and language acquisition are mostly neglected in the course of study of Latin (or

Ancient Greek) philology at German universities. Therefore, it is not surprising that the theory of the mental lexicon, corpus-based methods of vocabulary learning or the methods of natural language processing (NLP) are known just to a small minority of professionals. Thirdly, vocabulary acquisition receives almost no attention in learning materials nor in classes [5, p. 50], because it is said to be tedious and time-consuming. Generally, vocabulary learning is restricted to the homework, reduced to learning bilingual 'word equations' and finally tested in a completely context-free manner, despite suggestions to the contrary [5, 50-55].

For all these reasons, it seems appropriate to approach the identified problem of Latin vocabulary knowledge in an interdisciplinary research project of corpus linguistics, Latin pedagogy and computer science. Because of the missing theoretical and methodical foundations, we began our research by designing a model of Latin vocabulary acquisition according to the theory of the mental lexicon with three representation levels of a word (form, function, concept) [6, p. 56]. On this basis, we adapted the promising methodology of data-driven language learning [7] to Latin classes by using a design-based research approach [8]. Besides, the insights were used to develop a mobile-friendly software for creating corpus-based vocabulary exercises [9, 10] that facilitates personalised adaptive learning [11].

2 METHODOLOGY

Due to the lack of previous empirical data on Latin vocabulary acquisition, it was first necessary to gain primary data in a qualitative approach. Therefore, three intervention studies with 223 participants were carried out in two secondary schools in Berlin. Because of the educational context, the samples exhibit a self-selection bias, i.e. they were influenced by the choice of the teachers willing to collaborate. Generally, all studies had a corpus-based approach and a wide variety of vocabulary tasks (e.g. word formation or word meaning) in common. However, they differed in the degree of given context, the duration of the intervention (4 weeks up to 1 school year) and the Latin text corpus depending on the language level (beginners to intermediate learners) and age (10 to 17 years) of the participants. Following the first results, the software engineering focused on two main questions to implement the data-driven learning methodology:

1. a) How can we provide teachers with Latin texts that match the previous knowledge and experience of their students as closely as possible?
b) How can we (digitally) implement the data-driven learning methodology into Latin classes?
2. How can we prove that a context-based vocabulary approach supports the vocabulary acquisition just as much or more than the learning of simple word pairs?

2.1 Using NLP to create ideal exercises

To provide teachers (and students) with a wide variety of Latin texts, we settled for the free Perseus Library [12] because this repository has a well-defined API (Canonical Text Services [13]) and a standardized citation model (URN [14]) for ancient text passages, works and authors. However, if users are faced with a huge corpus, they need a way to prioritize the texts according to their personal needs.

Currently, this requirement is supported by offering a vocabulary filter and measures for text complexity. Within the vocabulary filter, the lemmata of a selected text are compared to a reference vocabulary that is essentially a lemmatized word frequency list derived from textbooks [15], treebanks [16] or materials created by publishing houses [17]. These reference vocabularies can be used to estimate the students' previous knowledge by specifying that e.g. the students should know the 500 most frequent words from that list. Hence, if teachers set a large corpus and the desired number of sentences, the software will rank all possible subsets of the corpus according to their congruence with the reference vocabulary. Thus, the filter gives teachers the opportunity to take at least in general into account their students' zone of proximal development [18, p. 238]. On the other hand, text complexity does not directly refer to a student's previous knowledge, but it supports an intrinsic comparison between multiple Latin texts by weighting different measures of the presumed degree of difficulty that readers may face when approaching a text, e.g. lexical density [19, p. 61]. Even though such measures offer just an approximation of actual complexity, they do allow for a formalised linguistic comparison that surpasses mere counting of words and integrates syntax, morphology and semantics [20, p. 607]. Consequently, using this measure, teachers can decide whether a selected text is suitable with regard to their students' linguistic and cognitive skills.

After committing themselves to a suitable text passage, teachers may not yet know the best target of a potential exercise. For that reason, we provide a keyword-in-context (KWIC) view to explore collocations and the specific usage of a particular word [21, p. 97]. The superficial token-based display is enriched by morpho-syntactic information, e.g. part of speech and dependency links. However, this enhanced KWIC view depends on well-curated Latin texts with scientific annotations, which are very few in number. To compensate for this shortcoming, we use an AI-driven dependency parser [22] to process plain Latin text in a fully automatic manner. It was trained as a multi-task classifier using representation learning on existing curated treebanks [23, p. 4291]. This is very reliable for basic tasks like tokenization, segmentation, lemmatization and part-of-speech tagging (>95% accuracy), but is rather error-prone (~80% accuracy) for dependency links. That is why the syntactic visualization in the KWIC view may be occasionally incorrect, but the basic concordance function and the information about parts of speech are highly accurate, thereby enabling teachers to create educational content in a much more well-informed manner.

Using such insights, teachers can choose one of various linguistic phenomena as a focus for their exercise, e.g. certain lemmata, parts of speech or syntactic properties. Besides, they may use various interaction types (e.g. cloze, matching, highlighting) and provide additional guidance or feedback. Finally, the software offers a fully functional preview of the exercise using H5P [24], an educational content framework that also offers automatic evaluation of exercise results.

2.2 Corpus-based Latin vocabulary learning

To advance toward answering our second research question, we started another study with students (in Berlin). For that reason, we built a digital intervention, the so-called vocabulary unit, by using our software tools and editing some parts manually, e.g. multiple-choice tasks on reading comprehension. As the unit should benefit all possible users, we had to make it work independently of the preceding learning environment (for the structure see table 1). Therefore, we enhanced the actual intervention setting (pre-test – intervention: exercise – post-test) with a text basis simulating a typical Latin class (text work). In doing so, we provide the same conditions for all students and show in an exemplary way how to implement vocabulary work in class, which is why the unit takes only about 40 minutes (= one lesson). Within this study, students should learn vocabulary that is part of the processed Latin text. The actual learning material (section 4, see table 1) consists either of cloze exercises built from the processed text (corpus-based learning) or of a word list with free text fields including all the words of the processed text (learning of word pair associations). Our hypothesis is that students perform better in the post-test if they have learnt the vocabulary in context (data-driven learning, e.g. in a cloze). The intervention, i.e. one of the two different variants, is given randomly to the users so that we are able to measure different learning outcomes depending on the assigned type of exercise. Nevertheless, there are some constraints to this intervention:

- We provide an extensive and occasionally quite challenging material to avoid the ceiling effect. The students get this information in the introduction to the unit. This way, they know that they will not be able to solve all tasks in the set time.
- We had to set for each section a timer, otherwise it would have been impossible to guarantee that each section is seen by all students. However, only tasks that have actually been seen are counted in the evaluation.
- We do not rate the tasks differently although we know that their cognitive complexity varies, e.g. between a multiple-choice task on morphology and one on semantics.
- We are rigorous while evaluating free-text tasks like fill-in-the-blanks. Even typing errors count as mistakes, because we want an automatic evaluation. On top of that, it is sometimes impossible to distinguish between a typing error and a lack of understanding.
- We do not offer an immediate feedback on each exercise. Therefore, the pre-test might have a priming effect, but the actual repetition of the tasks in the post-test cannot build upon a learning effect induced by feedback.
- We cannot easily measure the quality of long-term retention, because we are working with anonymous data and would need an even more elaborate framework to conduct longitudinal studies.

Due to all these constraints and a small data set (one group = 13 participants), the presented results are to be interpreted carefully. The sample size was deduced from the number of unique user IDs generated by H5P (see the full learner dataset at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3601182>). However, each ID technically represents just one piece of hardware (e.g. a mobile device) or, more precisely,

one piece of software (e.g. a browser or a mobile app). Thus, we cannot easily account for cases where multiple students share the same device or browser.

Table 1. Structure of the vocabulary unit.

Section	Description	Purpose	Interaction type	Duration
Pre-test	5 exercise types on different aspects of vocabulary knowledge, e.g. word formation or inflection	Testing vocabulary knowledge	Fill-in-the-blanks Multiple-choice (single or multiple answers)	4min
Latin text: Introduction and comprehension tasks	German introduction to the Latin text (Cicero, Ad Atticum I, 1, 8-10), noticing task (marking predicates), reading comprehension task using both a bilingual version and a German translation	Preparing the vocabulary exercise, ensuring text comprehension	Mark words Fill-in-the-blanks Multiple-choice (multiple answers)	18min
Exercise: Test and control group	Randomly sampled, the students practise vocabulary of the preceding tasks with clozes or a word list.	Learning vocabulary	Cloze (drag & drop) or Fill-in-the-blanks	12min
Post-test	See Pre-test	Measuring progress	See Pre-test	4min
Evaluation	Including only the completely finished tasks, analysis about the achieved scores in all sections and percentage change between tests	Feedback	Summary	--

3 RESULTS

3.1 General results (Figures 1 & 2)

In general, students who completed their tests very fast seem to exhibit a higher level of linguistic competence (see Fig. 1). Their speed of work may be deduced from the maximum possible score in their test results: A slow student's work often gets interrupted by the timer, which prevents him/her from spending too much time on certain sections (at the expense of others). Therefore, students with a high maximum possible score must have rarely suffered from running out of time. Incidentally, these students usually also made less mistakes, which implies that advanced learners do not only produce better test results, but also need less time to do so (see Fig. 2). In our case, the whole group was quite advanced, so the evaluation suffers heavily from the aforementioned ceiling effect. Therefore, we are not able to make fine-grained distinctions between those students whose performance was above average. Besides, not all students have seen all exercises. Thus, the performance indicators in the upcoming figures are not 100% reliable within specific sections of the study because they sometimes stem from results for different exercises. We accepted this shortcoming in order to increase the overall (i.e. cross-section) reliability of our exercises and, thus, the validity of the entire test.

Figure 1. Evaluation of vocabulary unit: Results are sorted by maximum possible score, e.g. the first user achieved about 70% of his/her maximum possible score of 81. A student's speed of work is correlated with the quality of his/her answers, i.e. faster students perform slightly better.

Figure 2. Students' speed and performance: Taking a lot of time to complete an exercise is correlated with worse results.

3.2 Task and outcome: Cloze vs. word list (Research Question 2)

As was pointed out above, our main focus in this study was to investigate the impact of context-dependent, corpus-based vocabulary learning on students' linguistic competence. To this end, we looked only at those exercise results that have been seen in both the pre-test and the post-test. Thus, if students failed to complete the entire pre-test because their time ran out, we also omit the corresponding results from the post-test because we cannot directly measure the change in performance for these exercises. Then, we split the data according to the randomly assigned type of intervention, i.e. roughly one half of the students received clozes as learning material, while the other half received a list of word equations. The vocabulary list roughly matches the traditional way of learning Latin in German schools: Students try to memorize German translations for single Latin words. In Fig. 3, we can see that most students show no development at all, which indicates that they either a) already achieved the highest score or b) failed completely in both the pre-test and the post-test. Usually, the former is the case, especially in highly advanced learner groups like in our case. This

case is not very interesting because there is not much room for improvement, except for providing harder exercises. The cases that deviated in the post-test are much more interesting: If there was a deviation, students who learned with vocabulary lists usually changed for the worse, while those with clozes usually improved. Notably, there are a few exceptions where cloze learners' performance decreased slightly, but there is only one example of a student who score a higher result for a specific exercise in the post-test. Thus, in general, learning vocabulary in context seems to be correlated with better performance on our linguistic test.

Figure 3. Comparison of students' performance before and after certain interventions. Larger markers indicate multiple students with the same percental change. Exercise IDs correspond to those in the learner dataset (see above). We may conclude that solving cloze exercises is correlated with substantial improvements in vocabulary competence, as opposed to traditional rote learning (using lists of bilingual word equations).

4 CONCLUSIONS

All in all, corpus-based vocabulary learning seems to be beneficial for a learner's lexical competence. If, like in our case, lexical competence is understood in a broader sense (e.g. including certain aspects of syntax and morphology), the performance improvements accordingly are not restricted to just matters of word choice or the translation of single words, but rather even to more complex tasks like reading comprehension or translation of multiword expressions. One reason for this relationship may be that relatively precise linguistic tasks like lemmatisation are often also a basic, but crucial part of more advanced workflows like the comprehension of literary texts. Other possible explanations include aspects like diversity and repetition: Often, the same words or similar phenomena are presented repeatedly, but with different types of interaction (e.g. fill-in-the-blanks vs. drag & drop) or from different linguistic viewpoints (e.g. syntax vs. morphology vs. lexis). This stems from our markedly broad understanding of vocabulary training, but also from the easy, uniform access to similar exercise types in the H5P framework.

Visualisations of learner data, esp. Fig. 2, might be a useful tool for teachers to evaluate whether their materials were adequate in various regards, e.g. the degree of difficulty or the time required to complete a given task. That is why we will consider integrating this kind of technology into the already existing evaluation section of our vocabulary unit. Furthermore, we would like to enable immediate feedback for the exercises, which had been excluded in this study to save time and thus include more exercises in the temporally restricted environment of high school teaching. In hindsight, however, it seems that fewer exercises (but with high-quality feedback) may be more suitable to answer our research questions because they potentially lead to greater changes in performance [25, p. 959]. Finally, the free-text exercises (fill-in-the-blanks) proved to be hard to evaluate automatically, so we need to define more flexible and more precise rules to determine the quality of a free-text answer.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The CALLIDUS project is funded by the German Research Foundation (project number 316618374) and lead by Malte Dreyer, Stefan Kipf and Anke Lüdeling. Also, we are thankful for the collaboration with teachers and students in Berlin who made the intervention studies possible.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] DESTATIS - Statistisches Bundesamt, *Schüler/-innen mit fremdsprachlichem Unterricht*. [Online] Available: <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bildung-Forschung-Kultur/Schulen/Tabellen/allgemeinbildende-beruflicheschulen-fremdsprachl-unterricht.html>. Accessed on: Jan. 02 2020.
- [2] P. Kuhlmann and H. Horstmann, *Wortschatz und Grammatik üben: Didaktische Kriterien und Praxisbeispiele für den Lateinunterricht*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2018.
- [3] *Einheitliche Prüfungsanforderungen in der Abiturprüfung - Latein: EPA*, 2005.
- [4] A. Beyer, "Im Lateinunterricht: „cupidine kommt von cupidi und ne ist Fragepartikel.“ – Wortschatzprobleme und ihre Ursachen," *Pegasus-Onlinezeitschrift*, vol. 19, 2019.
- [5] P. Kuhlmann, "Wortschatzlernen im Lateinunterricht - Mythen und Fakten," *Forum Schule*, vol. 63, pp. 40–56, 2016.
- [6] B. Höhle, Ed., *Psycholinguistik*. Berlin: Akademie Verlag, 2012.
- [7] T. Talai and Z. Fotovatnia, "Data-driven Learning: A Student-centered Technique for Language Learning," *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 1526–1531, 2012.
- [8] A. Bakker and D. van Eerde, "An introduction to design-based research with an example from statistics education," in *Advances in mathematics education, Approaches to qualitative research in mathematics education: Examples of methodology and methods*, A. Bikner-Ahsbahr, C. Knipping, and N. C. Presmeg, Eds., 2015, pp. 429–466.
- [9] G. Gilquin and S. Granger, "How can data-driven learning be used in language teaching," in *The Routledge handbook of corpus linguistics*, A. O’Keeffe and M. McCarthy, Eds., 2010, pp. 359–370.
- [10] A. Boulton, "Data-Driven Learning and Language Pedagogy," in *Encyclopedia of Language and Education, 3rd ed, Language, Education and Technology*, S. L. Thorne and S. May, Eds., 3rd ed., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017, pp. 181–192.
- [11] H. Peng, S. Ma, and J. M. Spector, "Personalized Adaptive Learning: An Emerging Pedagogical Approach Enabled by a Smart Learning Environment," in *Lecture Notes in Educational Technology, Foundations and trends in smart learning*, M. Chang, E. Popescu, and Kinshuk, Eds., Singapore: Springer Singapore, 2019, pp. 171–176.
- [12] B. Almas, A. Babeu, and A. Krohn, "Linked Data in the Perseus Digital Library," *ISAW Papers*, vol. 7, no. 3, <http://dlib.nyu.edu/awdl/isaw/isaw-papers/7/almas-babeu-krohn/>, 2014.
- [13] J. Tjepmar, C. Teichmann, G. Heyer, M. Berti, and G. Crane, "A new implementation for canonical text services [CTS]," in *Proceedings of the 8th Workshop on Language Technology for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, and Humanities (LaTeCH)*, 2014, pp. 1–8.
- [14] C. Blackwell and N. Smith, *The Canonical Text Services URN Specification, Version 2.0.Rc.1 [CITE / URN]*.
- [15] V. Bartoszek *et al.*, *VIVA 1 Lehrerband*: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2013.
- [16] D. Bamman and G. Crane, "The Ancient Greek and Latin Dependency Treebanks [AGLDT]," in *Language Technology for Cultural Heritage*: Springer, 2011, pp. 79–98.
- [17] C. Utz, "Mutter Latein und unsere Schüler - Überlegungen zu Umfang und Aufbau des Wortschatzes," in *Dialog - Klassische Sprachen und Literaturen, Antike Literatur - Mensch, Sprache, Welt*, P. Neukam, Ed., München, 2000, pp. 146–172.

- [18] K. Shabani, M. Khatib, and S. Ebadi, "Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development: Instructional Implications and Teachers' Professional Development," *English language teaching*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 237–248, 2010.
- [19] V. Johansson, "Lexical Diversity and Lexical Density in Speech and Writing: A Developmental Perspective," *Working Papers*, vol. 53, pp. 61–79, 2008.
- [20] M. A. Dascalu *et al.*, "ReaderBench: A Multi-Lingual Framework for Analyzing Text Complexity," in *Data Driven Approaches in Digital Education, Proc 12th European Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning, EC-TEL 2017*, 2017, pp. 606–609.
- [21] F. Helm, "Language and Culture in an Online Context: What Can Learner Diaries Tell Us about Intercultural Competence?," *Language and Intercultural Communication*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 91–104, 2009.
- [22] M. Straka and J. Straková, *UDPipe*.
- [23] M. Straka, J. Hajic, and J. Straková, "UDPipe: Trainable Pipeline for Processing CoNLL-U Files Performing Tokenization, Morphological Analysis, POS Tagging and Parsing," in *LREC*, 2016, pp. 4290–4297.
- [24] *H5P. Create, Share and Reuse Interactive HTML5 Content in Your Browser*. Tromsø, Norway.
- [25] B. Finn and J. Metcalfe, "Scaffolding Feedback to Maximize Long-Term Error Correction," *Memory & Cognition*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 951–961, 2010.